

ISic0545

I.Sicily inscription 0545

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object

unknown

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance

Found during expansion of the palazzo of the Principe di Rafaudale, Palermo, 1687

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, not located

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Aram Victoriae
2. Sex(tus) Pompeius Mer
3. cator VI(se)vir Aug(ustalis)
4. praeter summ[a]m
5. pro honore
6. d(onum) d(edit)
7. p(ecunia) s(ua) p(osuit)

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation**Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 491771

EDR 138301
EDCS 22000855

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7269 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 47

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